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BMD

Biodiversity Meets Data

MS13 First eDNA high-throughput datasets captured

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Summary

This milestone report documents the first implementation of high-throughput environmental DNA (eDNA) data capture within the Biodiversity Meets Data (BMD) project. The work contributes to Work Package 2 (WP2), which establishes the core data foundation of BMD by enabling high-throughput biodiversity data capture, mobilisation of legacy and newly generated datasets, and their integration into FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) biodiversity data infrastructures.

Within WP2, the activities reported here directly support Task 2.3 (High-throughput data capture & AI taxon identification), and specifically Subtask 2.3.2, which focuses on providing the stakeholder community with an end-to-end eDNA service. This service spans the full workflow from field sampling and metadata capture, through sequence processing and AI-supported taxonomic identification, to the publication of interoperable taxon occurrence data in international repositories.

The primary objective of Subtask 2.3.2 is to make eDNA-based biodiversity monitoring accessible as a scalable, standard-compliant service that can be seamlessly integrated into the wider BMD infrastructure. High-quality, well-curated eDNA datasets are essential both for operational biodiversity monitoring and for the development and validation of AI-based taxon identification services that underpin BMD's high-throughput monitoring toolbox.

This milestone, therefore, focuses on identifying, compiling, and curating the first set of high-throughput eDNA datasets suitable for mobilisation to the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), while simultaneously strengthening reference resources used for eukaryotic taxonomic assignment. The reported activities establish the initial operational workflows required to link eDNA data capture with AI-enabled taxonomic identification and FAIR data publication.

The datasets currently incorporated represent two complementary sources: (1) eDNA data generated during BMD stakeholder training and demonstration activities, and (2) selected legacy datasets recovered from the scientific literature and public sequence repositories. Together, these datasets form the foundational reference and benchmarking corpus required for the continued development, testing and scaling of the BMD eDNA identification service.

By delivering the first curated and mobilised eDNA datasets, this milestone marks a critical step towards BMD's overarching goal of enabling cost-effective, high-resolution, and standardised biodiversity monitoring across terrestrial, freshwater, and marine environments. It provides the practical data basis upon which downstream harmonisation, modelling, and Virtual Research Environment (VRE) analyses can be built, thereby supporting evidence-based conservation planning and policy implementation within and beyond the Natura 2000 network.

List of abbreviations

12S	12S ribosomal RNA gene
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ASV	Amplicon Sequence Variant
BMD	Biodiversity Meets Data
eDNA	Environmental DNA
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
LSU	Large Subunit of the ribosomal RNA gene, also known as 28S
ML	Machine Learning
ONT	Oxford Nanopore Technologies
OTU	Operational Taxonomic Unit
PacBio	Pacific Biosciences
rDNA ITS	Ribosomal DNA Internal Transcribed Spacer
SSU	Small Subunit of the ribosomal RNA gene, also known as 18S
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WP	Work package

1. Milestone description

Task Leaders: Naturalis (8), MeiseBG (2), UFC (2), UTartu (8), IHU (2), SGN (8), CNR (2), SIB (2)

The Biodiversity Meets Data (BMD) project¹ aims to develop a centralised digital platform, referred to as a Biodiversity Explorer, to support biodiversity conservation across Europe for natural resource managers and policymakers. The platform integrates high-throughput biodiversity tools with AI-based taxon identification services and provides tools and guidelines for mobilising both historical baseline data and newly generated high-throughput biodiversity data.

This milestone forms part of Work Package 2 (WP2: Data Catalogue, Data Mobilisation and High-throughput Data Capture), specifically Task 2.3, which aims to provide the stakeholder community with access to high-throughput methods for image and sound data capture as Plug-n-Play services (Subtask 2.3.1), as well as to facilitate eDNA sampling, and to provide AI taxon identification of the captured data as a service (Subtask 2.3.2). This milestone report documents the process and current status of identifying and curating relevant high-throughput environmental DNA (eDNA) datasets for mobilisation to the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)² while supporting the development of a reference dataset for the AI-based taxon identification service.

2. Progress towards milestone

2.1. Strategies for eDNA data capture and mobilisation to GBIF

eDNA data capture can involve a range of strategies, including the generation of new datasets through field sampling and high-throughput sequencing, the management of data produced across multiple projects, and the recovery of legacy³ datasets that are not readily accessible for reuse. While raw sequencing reads are often deposited in public repositories such as the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA)⁴, these data types are not directly usable as biodiversity occurrence records and require extensive bioinformatic processing, taxonomic assignment, and standardisation prior to reuse (Berry et al., 2020). Consequently, additional steps are needed to transform such sequencing data into interoperable and analysis-ready biodiversity information.

While it is important to collect, process, analyse, and publish new data in accordance with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016) and the principles of open science and open data, addressing legacy eDNA datasets embedded in peer-reviewed publications, supplementary materials of peer-reviewed articles and pre-prints, or obsolete repositories is equally important. Following curation to current standards, the integration and republication of such data to GBIF must be conducted with appropriate data governance and attribution.

Within our subtask and in this milestone report, we define “capturing” as either collecting new samples for eDNA analysis or identifying legacy datasets that have not yet been mobilised in a way that makes

¹ <https://bmd-project.eu/>

² <https://www.gbif.org/>

³ Note: “Legacy” indicates a previously published dataset that has not been mobilised to GBIF and is not included in the AI-based taxon identification reference dataset.

⁴ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/>

them readily usable as biodiversity occurrence data. The data processing steps for both strategies are described in Annex 1 of this report.

2.2. PlutoF platform for FAIR management of eDNA and ecological data

The PlutoF⁵ platform is a web-based research data management solution designed to support a wide range of biodiversity data types and projects across multiple fields, including ecology, taxonomy, environmental monitoring, nature conservation, agriculture, and genetics. It enables users to manage datasets throughout the entire data lifecycle—from project design and data collection to publication and archiving—in compliance with FAIR principles.

PlutoF supports the eDNA data management and mobilisation workflow⁶, including project planning, sample collection, metadata capture, quality control, and the publication of open data to ENA and GBIF. It provides a user-friendly and easily adoptable interface for preparing data for collaborative management and seamless publication. It was therefore chosen as the platform for eDNA data collection and management in the BMD workshops, as well as for curating and mobilising eDNA datasets relevant to this task to GBIF.

2.3. Dataset capture: Identification of relevant datasets

As part of this milestone, an evolving list of eDNA datasets (Table 1) has been created, including:

- (1) datasets generated during the project workshop “High-throughput biodiversity monitoring workshop - from camera trap data and eDNA sample to data in GBIF” (27-29 May 2026, Barcelona, Spain)⁷ and its sister course “From Water Samples to eDNA Identifications: PlutoF Workflows” held in Laelatu, Estonia (11-12 May 2026) for PhD students and early career researchers in Estonia;
- (2) curated legacy datasets identified through scientific literature or retrieved from ENA as sequencing data and subsequently republished to GBIF to support direct reuse.

All datasets reported in Table 1 were generated using third-generation long-read sequencing technologies, such as Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) and Pacific Biosciences (PacBio), which are increasingly being adopted for their high accuracy (i.e. low error rates) and high contiguity (Marx 2023). Therefore, the datasets presented in Table 1 that are being, or have already been, mobilised to GBIF are expected to be of the highest quality.

⁵ <https://plutof.ut.ee>

⁶ https://plutof.ut.ee/public/manuals/docs/PlutoF_eDNA_manual.pdf

⁷ <https://bmd-project.eu/news/>

Table 1. List of eDNA datasets to be captured and/or mobilised. A GBIF dataset DOI link is provided for datasets that were registered in GBIF during this subtask. “Samples mobilised” indicates the number of samples collected during the study, while “records mobilised” indicates the number of records already published in GBIF.

eDNA device	Sampling location	Dataset name	Project name	Target group	Target gene	GBIF dataset DOI	Samples mobilised	Records mobilised
PacBio Sequel II	Global	EUKARYO ME dataset	EUKARYO ME ⁸	Eukaryota	SSU, rDNA ITS, LSU	https://doi.org/10.15468/ehkbkt	10830	580009
PacBio Sequel II	Serbia	Targeted full-length 16S and ITS amplicon metagenomic profiling of drain-associated microbial communities	PRJNA1312468 ⁹	Fungi	rDNA ITS	In progress	2	
PacBio Sequel II	Estonia	Course “From Water Samples to eDNA Identifications: PlutoF Workflows”	NATARC ¹⁰ , BMD ¹¹	Eukaryota	COI, rDNA ITS, 12S, SSU	https://doi.org/10.15468/h95ncu	11	

⁸ <https://eukaryome.org/>

⁹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA1312468>

¹⁰ <https://natarc.ut.ee/uudised/kursus-keskkonna-dna-laellatu.php?lang=en>

¹¹ <https://bmd-project.eu/>

eDNA device	Sampling location	Dataset name	Project name	Target group	Target gene	GBIF dataset DOI	Samples mobilised	Records mobilised
PacBio Sequel II	Spain	Biodiversity Meets Data: High-throughput biodiversity monitoring workshop - from camera trap data and eDNA sample to data in GBIF	BMD ¹²	Eukaryota	CO1, rDNA ITS, 12S, SSU	https://doi.org/10.15468/mu2vby	15	
PacBio Sequel II and Revio	Global	Global standardised soil eukaryome dataset (GloSED)	GloSED ¹³	Eukaryota	rDNA ITS	Planned	>4000	
PacBio Sequel	Global (UK)	Long-read metabarcoding of the eukaryotic rDNA operon to phylogenetically and taxonomically resolve environmental diversity ¹⁴	PRJEB25197 ¹⁵	Eukaryota	SSU, rDNA ITS, LSU	In progress	3	

¹² <https://bmd-project.eu/>

¹³ <https://github.com/Mycology-Microbiology-Center/GloSED>

¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.13117>

¹⁵ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB25197>

eDNA device	Sampling location	Dataset name	Project name	Target group	Target gene	GBIF dataset DOI	Samples mobilised	Records mobilised
PacBio Sequel II	Global	Global patterns and rates of habitat transitions across the eukaryotic tree of life ¹⁶	PRJEB45931 ¹⁷	Eukaryota	SSU, rDNA ITS, LSU	https://doi.org/10.15468/whq9w3	18	
MiSeq V2/V3	Austria	eLTER Austria - Insects	eLTER Austria	Insects	COI	in preparation	200	Approx. 45000
MiSeq V3, NovaSeq SP, NovaSeq X	Austria	eLTER Austria - Soil eDNA	eLTER Austria	Fungi, Invertebrates, Bacteria	Bacteria 16S rRNA; Fungi 18S ITS rRNA; Invertebrates COI.intF and COI.2198	in preparation	32	Not available

2.3.1. Datasets generated during the project workshop

The project stakeholder workshop “High-throughput biodiversity monitoring workshop – from camera trap data and eDNA sample to data in GBIF” took place from 27 to 29 May 2026 in Barcelona, Spain. It was a three-day hands-on workshop for Natura 2000 site managers and EU conservation practitioners, aiming to build capacity in the use of new biodiversity monitoring devices and AI-based analysis tools. During the workshop, participants were trained in the collection and processing of freshwater samples in accordance with established standardised protocols (Panksep et al., 2025; Panksep et al., 2023), as well as in the management, analysis, and publication of data generated throughout the project workflow to international repositories, including ENA and GBIF. Fifteen water samples were collected in the Natural Park of Sant Llorenç del Munt i l'Obac (Bassa de la Mata, Figure 1).

For the samples collected during the workshop, necessary laboratory procedures, such as DNA extraction and amplification of the target DNA region, will be carried out in the Molecular Mycology Lab of the University of Tartu, Institute of Ecology and Earth Sciences, Tartu, Estonia. Sequencing will be performed using the PacBio Sequel II next-generation sequencing system. While workshop participants were trained to analyse and publish eDNA data using test datasets during the workshop, the actual eDNA data generated from the collected samples will be uploaded to PlutoF and mobilised to GBIF after the

¹⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-022-01838-4>

¹⁷ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB45931>

required laboratory processing, data quality checks, and data analysis steps have been completed in Tartu. The DNA-derived occurrence dataset resulting from this course will be available in GBIF at <https://www.gbif.org/dataset/0c0b12c5-1e20-4252-9572-b42d3d69559a>.

Figure 1. Photographs of water sampling during the BMD workshop at the Natural Park of Sant Llorenç del Munt i l'Obac (Bassa de la Mata), Spain.

The same course, entitled “From Water Samples to eDNA Identifications: PlutoF Workflows”, was held from 11 to 12 May 2026 in Laelatu, Estonia, as a sister course to the BMD workshop for PhD students and early-career researchers in Estonia (Figure 2). The purpose of this course was to verify all steps of the workshop prior to delivering the workflow to a wider audience. Ten marine water samples and one sediment sample were collected during the course and will be processed and analysed in the same way as the samples collected during the BMD workshop in Barcelona, Spain. The DNA-derived occurrence dataset resulting from this course will be available in GBIF at <https://www.gbif.org/dataset/af4c5d8c-9ada-4663-b854-b96a88c663a8>.

Figure 2. Photographs of marine water sampling during the course “From Water Samples to eDNA Identifications: PlutoF Workflows” in Laelatu, Estonia.

The bioinformatics workflow for processing raw data from these workshops is presented in Annex 2 of this report.

2.3.2. Legacy datasets

Relevant legacy eDNA datasets were identified by targeting datasets with broad taxonomic coverage and representing samples from diverse habitats. In addition, ENA Browser Advanced Search¹⁸ with appropriate filters was used to identify datasets (raw reads) that (1) targeted the ribosomal DNA operon, (2) focused on eukaryotes, (3) employed third-generation sequencing technologies, such as PacBio and Oxford Nanopore Technologies, and (4) included samples from Europe. The corresponding ENA search query was -

```
environmental_sample=true
AND geo_box1(29.1785,-52.2969,71.7608,49.7031)
AND (instrument_platform="pacbio_smrt" OR
instrument_platform="oxford_nanopore")
AND (target_gene="Eukaryotic ribosomal DNA operon" OR target_gene="18S" OR
target_gene="28S")
```

The search resulted in two projects (PRJEB45931 and PRJEB25197) comprising ten samples from Europe (Figure 3), but this number is expected to increase in the coming years, as additional keyword-based searches for samples and projects indicate that several studies matching the search criteria exist for

¹⁸ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/advanced-search>

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which raw data have not yet been made publicly available. The third-generation sequencing technologies are still relatively new in the field, particularly Oxford Nanopore Technologies with its MinION platform, and the majority of studies in which they have been used have not yet been published.

The screenshot shows the ENA Browser Advanced Search interface. At the top, there is a search bar with the text "Enter text search terms" and a search icon. Below it, there are examples of search terms: "histone_BN000065" and "Enter accession" with a "View" icon. Further down, there are more examples: "Taxon:9606, BN000065, PRJEB402". The interface includes navigation links for Home, Submit, Search, About, and Support. The main heading is "Advanced Search" with links for "How to use this service" and "API Documentation". Below the heading, there is a brief description of the search process and a list of search criteria: Data Type, Query, Inclusion/Exclusion, Fields, Data Filters, and Results. There are also links for "Download ENA records" (XML) and "Download report" (JSON, TSV). The search results are displayed in a table with the following columns: Run Accession, Description, Instrument Platform, Environmental Sample, Location, and Target Gene. The table contains 10 rows of data, all of which are Sequel II sequencing runs using the PACBIO_SMRT platform, targeting the Eukaryotic ribosomal DNA operon. The locations are in Europe, with coordinates ranging from 55.3 N 3.43 E to 64.24 N 19.76 E. The environmental sample status is "true" for all runs.

Run Accession	Description	Instrument Platform	Environmental Sample	Location	Target Gene
ERR6454469	Sequel II sequencing	PACBIO_SMRT	true	60.49 N 16.3 E	Eukaryotic ribosomal DNA operon
ERR6454470	Sequel II sequencing	PACBIO_SMRT	true	56.66 N 12.11 E	Eukaryotic ribosomal DNA operon
ERR6454462	Sequel II sequencing	PACBIO_SMRT	true	58.37 N 12.16 E	Eukaryotic ribosomal DNA operon
ERR6454466	Sequel II sequencing	PACBIO_SMRT	true	58.37 N 12.16 E	Eukaryotic ribosomal DNA operon
ERR6454467	Sequel II sequencing	PACBIO_SMRT	true	64.24 N 19.76 E	Eukaryotic ribosomal DNA operon
ERR6454461	Sequel II sequencing	PACBIO_SMRT	true	59.83 N 18.63 E	Eukaryotic ribosomal DNA operon
ERR6454463	Sequel II sequencing	PACBIO_SMRT	true	64.24 N 19.76 E	Eukaryotic ribosomal DNA operon
ERR6454465	Sequel II sequencing	PACBIO_SMRT	true	59.83 N 18.63 E	Eukaryotic ribosomal DNA operon
ERR2355432	Sequel sequencing	PACBIO_SMRT	true	52.22 N 0.81 W	18S
ERR2355433	Sequel sequencing	PACBIO_SMRT	true	55.3 N 3.43 E	18S

Figure 3. ENA Browser Advanced search for raw sequences originating from eDNA samples collected from Europe and targeting the ribosomal DNA operon.

For all legacy datasets listed in Table 1, sample metadata were imported into the PlutoF platform, and amplicon sequence variants (ASVs; representing unique, quality-filtered sequences without clustering) or operational taxonomic unit (OTU) representative sequences (i.e., sequences representing clusters of similar reads grouped by a predefined similarity threshold), derived from raw sequence data, were uploaded and linked to the corresponding samples. Each dataset was registered with GBIF, and the data hosted in PlutoF were subsequently published in GBIF as DNA-derived data. For datasets in which

ASV/OTU representative sequences were not readily available, representative sequences were generated from raw sequence data deposited in ENA by applying the same data processing protocols used for sequence data generated during the BMD stakeholder workshop (Section 2.2.1).

These datasets will also contribute to the reference dataset for the AI-based taxon identification service (Subtask 2.3.2).

3. Improving eukaryotic taxonomic assignment

eDNA-based biodiversity monitoring has fundamentally expanded the scope of detectable biodiversity by enabling the observation of organisms that are rare, cryptic, microscopic, or otherwise difficult to survey using traditional methods (Thomsen and Willerslev, 2015; Valentini et al., 2016; Ota et al., 2020). As a result, eDNA surveys routinely recover large proportions of sequence data that cannot be confidently assigned to known species, particularly in taxonomically complex groups such as fungi, protists, and other early-diverging eukaryotes (Tedersoo et al., 2022). Addressing this challenge is a central objective of Subtask 2.3.2, which aims to provide an operational eDNA sampling and identification service based on robust, transparent, and scalable taxonomic assignment workflows.

Within Subtask 2.3.2, taxonomic assignment is not treated as a standalone bioinformatic step, but as an integrated service component that links sequence data, reference databases, AI-based classifiers, and data publication pipelines. High-throughput eDNA data only become actionable for biodiversity monitoring, reporting, and modelling once sequence variants can be reliably interpreted and communicated in a standardised and reproducible way. Improving eukaryotic taxonomic assignment is therefore essential for transforming raw sequence output into FAIR biodiversity information suitable for use across the BMD infrastructure.

A persistent limitation of many eDNA studies is their reliance on short barcode markers (such as partial rDNA ITS regions), which often lack sufficient phylogenetic signal to resolve deep or poorly sampled lineages. This leads to large fractions of sequence data being classified only at high taxonomic ranks or reported as “unidentified eukaryotes”. In the context of Task 2.3, such limitations directly constrain the performance of AI-based taxon identification services and reduce the interpretability of monitoring results delivered to stakeholders.

The activities reported under this milestone contribute to Subtask 2.3.2 by strengthening the reference and training data foundation required for improved taxonomic inference from eDNA. The curated high-throughput datasets mobilised here prioritise long-read and multi-locus sequencing approaches (e.g. full-length rDNA operons), which provide substantially greater taxonomic and phylogenetic resolution. These datasets are essential inputs both for conventional reference-based identification and for the development, benchmarking, and validation of machine-learning classifiers used in the BMD eDNA service.

In addition, Subtask 2.3.2 explicitly aims to ensure that taxonomic identification results are traceable, versioned, and reproducible over time. Taxonomic concepts are dynamic, and sequence assignments may change as reference databases evolve or classification models improve. To address this, the eDNA curation and mobilisation workflows applied in this milestone include systematic re-identification of sequences, explicit documentation of reference databases and classifier versions used, and preservation of taxonomic identification histories. This approach supports both scientific transparency and long-term reuse of the data within BMD and by external users.

By mobilising curated eDNA datasets to GBIF and ENA with clearly documented taxonomic workflows, this milestone directly enables downstream harmonisation activities in WP3 and integration into Virtual Research Environments (WP5). At the same time, it provides concrete, high-quality examples of how eDNA-derived taxon occurrence data can be reliably generated and published as part of an operational eDNA identification service. In this way, the improvements to eukaryotic taxonomic assignment described here are a critical enabler of Subtask 2.3.2 goal to deliver AI-supported, end-to-end eDNA biodiversity monitoring as a service for the BMD stakeholder community.

4. Further work

Future work will focus on expanding the portfolio of high-throughput eDNA datasets, while continuing the curation, standardisation, and regular updating of already incorporated datasets. In parallel, all mobilised data will be systematically integrated into the operational development of the AI-based taxon identification service within Subtask 2.3.2. In particular, emphasis will be placed on strengthening the interoperability between eDNA data capture workflows, reference database development, and machine-learning-based classification approaches, ensuring that the service can be delivered in a robust, scalable, and user-oriented manner.

A substantial part of the forthcoming work will be carried out in close collaboration with the wider BMD consortium, reflecting the cross-cutting nature of Task 2.3 within the project. Joint activities with WP1 (user requirements and stakeholder engagement) will support the refinement of eDNA workflows and services based on feedback from end-users, including Natura 2000 site managers and other biodiversity monitoring practitioners. At the same time, collaboration with WP3 (data harmonisation and integration) will ensure that mobilised eDNA datasets are aligned with common standards and interoperable with other data streams within the BMD data infrastructure, while interactions with WP5 (Virtual Research Environments) will facilitate the integration of eDNA-derived data products into analytical and modelling pipelines.

Capacity building and knowledge transfer will remain a central component of Subtask 2.3.2. Future activities will therefore include coordinated training and outreach efforts with WP7, such as workshops, technical training sessions, and dissemination activities designed to promote the adoption of FAIR, standardised eDNA data workflows across the stakeholder community. These activities will build upon the initial stakeholder training events and further demonstrate how high-throughput eDNA monitoring and AI-supported taxonomic identification can be implemented in practice.

In addition, continued efforts will be directed towards the identification and mobilisation of new datasets, including both newly generated data and high-value legacy resources, as well as towards iterative improvement of taxonomic assignment workflows through re-analysis and incorporation of updated reference data. Through these combined activities, the work under Subtask 2.3.2 will contribute to the progressive maturation of the BMD eDNA service, ensuring its integration with the broader project architecture and its long-term applicability for large-scale, standardised biodiversity monitoring.

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5. Annex

Annex 1. Data processing steps for capturing and mobilising eDNA data

Newly collected samples

Steps applied:

- (1) Sampling and collection of sample metadata using the PlutoF GO app
- (2) DNA extraction
- (3) Amplification of the target DNA region (COI, ITS, 18S, 12S)
- (4) Sequencing
- (5) Processing of raw sequence data to obtain ASVs/OTU representative sequences
- (6) Taxonomic assignment
- (7) Uploading ASVs/OTU representative sequences to the PlutoF platform
- (8) Uploading samples to ENA/BioSamples
- (9) Uploading raw sequence data to ENA
- (10) Publishing ASVs/OTU representative sequences to GBIF as a DNA-derived taxon occurrence dataset

Legacy datasets

Steps applied:

- (1) Collection of sample metadata and sequence data from scientific articles or from the ENA raw sequence data repository (with the PlutoF platform used for data storage and management)
- (2) Processing of raw sequence data to obtain ASVs/OTU representative sequences (if required)
- (3) Taxonomic assignment (if required)
- (4) Uploading ASVs/OTU representative sequences to the PlutoF platform
- (5) Publishing ASVs/OTU representative sequences to GBIF as a DNA-derived taxon occurrence dataset

Annex 2. Bioinformatics workflow for processing raw eDNA sequence data

The following steps were applied to process raw sequence data from the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA):

1. Demultiplexed single-end data (PacBio) were analysed using the PipeCraft2 tool (Anslan et al., 2017) and the NextITS pipeline (Mikryukov et al., 2026) within it with default parameters:

2. Initial taxonomic assignments were obtained using the SINTAX (Edgar et al., 2016) classifier with the default parameters available under the *Quick Tools* → *assign taxonomy* menu in PipeCraft2:

- Using the Python script below, the resulting OTU table and FASTA file containing OTU representative sequences and their taxonomic assignments were converted into CSV format suitable for import into PlutoF and linked to the corresponding material samples:

```
#!/usr/bin/python

import csv
from Bio import SeqIO
from pathlib import Path

# Settings
parent_dir = Path.cwd()
indata_dir = parent_dir / "Step2_Results" / "05.LULU"
taxonomy_dir = parent_dir / "taxonomy_out.sintax"
outdata_dir = parent_dir / "outdata"

infile_otus = indata_dir / "OTU_table_LULU.txt"
infile_fasta = indata_dir / "OTUs_LULU.fa"
taxon_assignments = taxonomy_dir / "taxonomy.sintax.txt"

project_name = "Biodiversity Meets Data workshop 2026"
sample_type = "materialsampl"
seq_region = "ITS1;5.8S;ITS2"

separate_files = False # <- set to False for single output file
```



```

ct = 0

# Header for all outputs
output_header = [
    "Sequence ID",
    "Linked to.ID",
    "Linked to.Type",
    "Linked to.Project",
    "Sequence",
    "Traits.Number of reads per sample.Value",
    "Sampling event.Sampling area.Country",
    "Determination.Taxon name",
    "Sequenced regions"
]

# read in sequences in FASTA format
seq_dict = {}
with open(infile_fasta, "r") as handle:
    for record in SeqIO.parse(handle, "fasta"):
        record_id = str(record.id)
        seq = str(record.seq)
        seq_dict[record_id] = seq

# read in taxonomic assignments
tax_dict = {}
with open(taxon_assignments, "r") as source_tax:
    dataReader = csv.reader(source_tax, delimiter="\t")
    for row in dataReader:
        taxonomy = row[3]
        if taxonomy and not taxonomy == "":
            tax_levels = taxonomy.split(",")
            tax_last_element = tax_levels[-1][2:]
            tax_last_element = tax_last_element.replace("_", " ")
            tax_dict[row[0]] = tax_last_element

with open(infile_otus, "r") as source:
    dataReader = csv.reader(source, delimiter="\t")

    header = next(dataReader)
    sample_columns = header[1:]

# Prepare writers
writers = {}
files = {}

if separate_files:
    # Create one file per sample
    for i, sample_name in enumerate(sample_columns):
        # sample_id = f"BMD_W_{str(i).zfill(7)}"
        safe_name = sample_name.replace(" ", "_")
        outfile = outdata_dir / f"{safe_name}.csv"

```



```
f = open(outfile, "w", newline="")
writer = csv.writer(f)
writer.writerow(output_header)

writers[i] = writer
files[i] = f
else:
    # Single file mode
    outfile = outdata_dir / "sequences4import.csv"
    f = open(outfile, "w", newline="")
    writer = csv.writer(f)
    writer.writerow(output_header)

# Process data
for row in dataReader:
    ct += 1

    otu_id = row[0]
    sequence = seq_dict.get(otu_id, "")
    taxon_name = tax_dict.get(otu_id, "")

    for i, value in enumerate(row[1:]):
        try:
            count = int(value)
        except ValueError:
            continue

    if count > 0:
        # sample_id = f"BMD_W_{str(i).zfill(7)}"
        sample_id = sample_columns[i]
        sequence_id = f"{otu_id}_{sample_id}"

        output_row = [
            sequence_id,
            sample_id,
            sample_type,
            project_name,
            sequence,
            count,
            "",
            taxon_name,
            seq_region
        ]

        if separate_files:
            writers[i].writerow(output_row)
        else:
            writer.writerow(output_row)

# Close files
if separate_files:
```



```
        for f in files.values():
            f.close()
    else:
        f.close()

print("No of rows processed:", ct)
```

4. A CSV file containing OTU representative sequences was uploaded to PlutoF. This was followed by two analyses in the PlutoF analysis module: the **SH Matching (v2.0.0)** tool (Abarenkov et al., 2022) to obtain UNITE Species Hypothesis (SH) codes, and the **ML-based taxon prediction v3[dynamic]** (Abarenkov et al., unpublished) to manually verify and potentially improve the taxonomic annotations obtained using the SINTAX classifier in workflow step 2.

